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THE ROLE OF CELLULOSE NANOCRYSTALS IN BIOCOMPATIBLE STARCH-BASED CLICKED NANOCOMPOSITE HYDROGELS

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Abstract

Starch-based nanocomposite hydrogels were successfully prepared by the Diels-Alder click cross-linking reaction between furan-functionalized starch derivative and a water-soluble tetrafunctional maleimide compound, adding cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) as nanoreinforcement. The effect of increasing the CNC content on rheological and swelling properties as well as on the morphology of

the hydrogels was analyzed. Besides, in order to evaluate the applicability of the as-prepared hydrogels as delivery systems, drug release measurements and *in vitro* cytotoxicity assays were also performed. It was found that the prepared nanocomposite hydrogels presented higher stiffness as the CNC content increased. The incorporation of the nanocrystals modified the internal porous microstructure of the hydrogels, affecting consequently both the swelling capacity and the drug-delivery kinetics. Moreover, the prepared nanocomposite hydrogels showed non-toxic behavior, demonstrating their potential applicability in the biomedical field, especially as sustained drug delivery systems.

Keywords

Starch-based hydrogel, Diels-Alder, Cellulose nanocrystals.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, researches focusing on the development of biomaterials are facing new challenges that the biomedicine requires, mainly related to enhanced cytocompatibility, antimicrobial properties, bioactivity, biodegradability and non-toxicity [1–3]. Besides, they should be easily fabricated into different shapes [2] and should also present high biological stability and good resistance to chemical substances in the body, as well as improved mechanical properties [4]. In this line of investigation, hydrogels have emerged as excellent alternative materials for being used in numerous applications in the biomedical field, as biological scaffolds for tissue engineering or diagnostic or drug and gene delivery devices, among others [4–7]. Regarding the requirements for delivery system for sustained release, hydrogels should present the capacity to deliver and release an active drug with minimum side-effects, optimal response and prolonged efficacy, and the drug is intended to act directly in the damaged area without affecting other tissues and organs [8]. Obviously, the amount of drug loaded into the hydrogel and the subsequent release and efficiency is going to be strongly conditioned by

the nature of the polymer, the final microstructure and porosity, the cross-linking density and the affinity with the swollen media [8,9].

As previously defined elsewhere [10], hydrogels are three-dimensional (3D) hydrophilic polymeric networks which are able to swell and retain large amount of water or biological fluids, maintaining their specific 3D structure in aqueous media. Physical hydrogels are formed due to secondary side inter- and intramolecular forces as hydrogen bonds, electrostatic forces or hydrophobic interactions, along with physical entanglements of the polymeric chains. Chemical hydrogels are those including covalent crosslinking between main chains, commonly performed by conventional chemical reactions leading to tailor-made hydrogels. However, although the chemical hydrogels are often preferred due to their better mechanical performance and stability, in many cases the biocompatibility of the resulting materials could be compromised due to the use of toxic reagents [11]. Besides, the employment of some of these reactions involves the use of strong reaction conditions, the appearance of side reactions and low coupling efficiency [12–14]. These inconveniences restrict the application areas of the developed materials [13]. During the last years, numerous authors have proposed the click chemistry as good alternative to the most conventional chemical reactions. Among the different click reactions, the Diels-Alder (DA) reaction, i.e. a thermoreversible [4 + 2] cycloaddition between a diene and a dienophile [11,15], is one of the most interesting options for the development of hydrogels for biomedical applications [1,9] since the reaction could be performed in aqueous media, without catalysts and under mild reaction conditions [4,11]. Indeed, several investigations employing the DA reaction for the synthesis of different type of hydrogels have been recently reported, presenting stable network structures [4] and interesting mechanical and rheological properties [1,6,16].

Hydrogels could also be classified according to the nature of the polymer, i.e. synthetic or natural polymer, and the use of the latter instead of those derived from petroleum is gaining attention as

their use normally ensures the biocompatibility of the resulting hydrogels [17,18]. In this sense, in the last years, several biopolymers had been investigated for the formation of hydrogels, mainly proteins (collagen or gelatin) or polysaccharides (hyaluronic acid, alginate, chitosan, etc.) [5] in some cases using click chemistry reactions. Recently, Kramer et al. [19] reported the preparation of DA thermally reversible hydrogels based on nanocellulose suitable for the fabrication of biomedical devices by 3D printing. Besides, Guaresti et al. [20,21] proposed different strategies to obtain hydrogels from chitosan by using the DA reaction, with promising results for applications on drug delivery systems. In contrast, only little works of starch-based DA hydrogels had been published in literature. In our previous work [10], biobased hydrogels with promising antimicrobial and electrical properties for future biomedical applications were prepared based on furan-modified starch.

However, biopolymer-based hydrogels present some drawbacks comparing with the synthetic ones, being the less mechanical robustness one of the most limiting factor. Therefore, the development of bionanocomposite hydrogels to obtain more competitive biopolymer-based hydrogels is often proposed [22] and, in contrast to inorganic nanofillers, cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) have gained attention for biomedical applications due to its sustainable character, mechanical properties, biocompatibility, biodegradability and low cytotoxicity [22,23]. The incorporation of CNC could improve the mechanical behavior and the dimensional stability of hydrogels [22,23] and display effects on the gelation mechanism and the drug release [23] due to its high crystallinity, aspect ratio and nanoscale fibrillar geometry [24,25] as well as the ability to form inter- and intramolecular interactions [23].

The aim of the present research was the development and characterization of starch-based hydrogels suitable for be used as biomaterial for controlled drug delivery. With that purpose, hydrogels and their nanocomposites were obtained by DA reaction between the synthesized furan-modified starch

derivative and commercial PEG-based tetrafunctional maleimide as cross-linker, adding CNC as nanoreinforcement. The influence of the CNCs content on the rheological and swelling properties as well as on the morphology of the hydrogels was analyzed. Besides, drug delivery measurements were performed using chloramphenicol (ClPh), a broad spectrum synthetic antibiotic, water-soluble and which is rapidly absorbed by the body, as a model drug. Finally, cytotoxicity assays were carried out in order to assess the biocompatibility of the developed novel hydrogels.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Normal maize starch containing 73 wt.% amylopectin and 27 wt.% amylose, furfuryl isocyanate (97%) and 4arm-PEG10K (number-average molar mass = 10,000 g mol⁻¹) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA) and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, for analysis) from Panreac (Spain). Microcrystalline cellulose (from Sigma-Aldrich) and sulfuric acid (from Panreac, 96%) were used to extract CNCs. The phosphate buffered saline (PBS) tablets were purchased from Panreac. Besides, for short-term cytotoxicity assays the following reactants were additionally used: L929 mouse fibroblast cells (clon 929 of the NCTC:CCL from American Type Culture Collection, ATCC), minimum essential medium containing Earle salts and L-glutamine 2mM, non-essential amino acids and sodic pyruvate (from Gibco®, USA), penicillin and streptomycin (provided by Lonza, USA), fetal bovine serum (supplied by Biochor, USA) and DMSO from Sigma-Aldrich. Distilled water was used as solvent. All reagents and solvents were employed as received.

2.2. Preparation of cellulose nanocrystals (CNC)

The extraction of the crystalline parts of the microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) was performed by acidic hydrolysis following the procedure reported elsewhere [26]. 5 g of MCC were treated with sulfuric acid 64 wt.% aqueous solution. The reaction was carried out during 30 min at 45 °C with continuous

magnetic stirring. After that period, the suspension was diluted with distilled water to stop the reaction and avoid the undesired degradation of the sample. Then, the acidity was reduced by centrifugation (twice, 4,500 rpm, 20 min) and the precipitate was then neutralized by dialysis (Spectra Pro 12,000–14,000 MWCO regenerated cellulose dialysis membranes from Spectrum Laboratories, USA) against distilled water for 5 days. Finally, the suspension was ultrasonicated for 15 min and then freeze-dried until being used.

2.3. Synthesis of furanic starch derivative (S-FI)

Starch was modified by the reaction of gelatinized starch (S) with furfuryl isocyanate (FI) following the method reported previously [10] (Scheme 1). Firstly, normal maize starch was gelatinized with water for 40 min at 90 °C. After that period, the resulting gel was cooled down, homogenized (POLYTRON® PT 2500 E) and dried (70 °C, 5 h).

Then, 0.45 g of the gelatinized dried starch were dissolved in 6.4 mL of DMSO and reacted with the corresponding amount of furfuryl isocyanate (1:0.1 S:FI molar ratio, based on the molecular weight of anhydroglucose unit 162 g mol^{-1}) for 2 h at 60 °C. After that time, the product was precipitated and washed with ethanol, dissolved in distilled water and purified by dialysis (Spectra Pro 12,000–14,000 MWCO regenerated cellulose dialysis membranes from Spectrum Laboratories, USA) against distilled water for 24 h. Finally, the resulting product was dried at 30 °C for 24 h.

Scheme 1 – Synthesis of furan-modified starch.

2.4. Hydrogel formation by DA reaction between S-FI and TTMI

Starch-based clicked hydrogels were obtained by the DA reaction between the S-FI derivative and a commercial water-soluble PEG-based tetramaleimide (TTMI) (Schemes 2 and 3). Firstly, 0.128 g of S-FI were dissolved in distilled water (6 wt.%) overnight and then 0.064 g of TTMI were added (furan to maleimide (Fu:Mal) weight ratio of 1:0.5). The reaction was proceeded at 65 °C for 24 h in a close vial. Hereafter the resulting hydrogel will be named as HSF14.

Scheme 2 – Chemical structure of the used tetrafunctional water-soluble TTMI cross-linker.

Scheme 3 – DA cross-linking reaction between S-FI and TTMI.

2.5. Preparation of nanocomposites based on DA hydrogel

The nanocomposite hydrogels were prepared by adding different CNC contents (i.e. 2.5 and 5 wt.% relative to the S-FI plus TTMI total weight) into the hydrogel reactive mixture. For that, as described above for the neat hydrogel, 0.128 g of S-FI were dissolved in the distilled water (6 wt.%) overnight and the desired amount of CNC was incorporated to the solution, previously dispersed in distilled water by ultrasonication. The water content required for the dispersion of CNCs was considered in order to maintain constant the final water content of the samples. Then, 0.064 g of TTMI were added

and the reaction was conducted at 65 °C for 24 h in a close vial. As in case of the non-reinforced hydrogels, the 1:0.5 Fu:Mal ratio was used to prepare the hydrogel nanocomposites. The cross-linked nanocomposite hydrogels will be referred as HSF14 plus the nanocrystal content, i.e. HSF14 - 2.5CNC and HSF14 - 5CNC.

2.6. Characterization

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements were performed in a Nicolet Nexus spectrophotometer. Measurements were recorded in the range from 4000 cm^{-1} to 650 cm^{-1} in attenuated reflection mode, with a 4 cm^{-1} resolution and 32 scans. The spectra were recorded with a Specac MKII Golden Gate accessory equipped with a diamond crystal at a nominal incident angle of 45 degrees and ZnSe lens.

Ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy (UV-vis spectroscopy) was used to follow the DA reaction between the furan-modified starch and the tetramaleimide cross-linker. The reaction was monitored using a Shimadzu UV-3600/3100 instrument equipped with a thermoelectric cell holder, operating at 65 °C in a range of 200 to 400 nm and recording spectra every 30 min during a total period of 24 h.

The rheological study of the hydrogels was performed (the measurements were conducted in triplicate, $n = 3$) in a Scientific Advanced Rheometric Expansion System (ARES) using plate-plate geometry (25 mm diameter). Frequency sweep measurements were performed at 37 °C from 0.1 to 500 rad s^{-1} at a fixed strain, in the linear viscoelastic region, previously assessed by strain sweep experiments.

The swelling capacity of the hydrogels ($n = 3$) was determined by general gravimetric method. Freeze-dried hydrogels were incubated at 37 °C until equilibrium using simulated intestinal fluid, PBS at pH = 7.4. At selected time intervals, the swollen hydrogel samples were taken out from the solution, the

excess of water was gently removed with a filter paper and weighed. The swelling ratio (SR) was determined by Eq. (1):

$$SR (\%) = \frac{W_s - W_t}{W_t} \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where W_s is the weight of the swollen sample and W_t is the weight of the final dried sample. The equilibrium swelling value was considered to be achieved when the weight of the hydrogels no longer increased.

In vitro release study was performed in PBS using chloramphenicol (CIPh) as the model drug. Freeze-dried hydrogel samples were loaded with the drug (0.5 mg CIPh mL⁻¹ PBS solution) at 25 °C for 3 h (time stated based on the equilibrium swelling times data from the swelling studies). After the immersion time, samples were dried at room temperature until constant weight. For the release studies, the dried loaded hydrogel samples were introduced in a metallic perforated bag and stirred in 80 mL of PBS solution (pH = 7.4) at 37 °C. At selected time intervals, an aliquot of 1 mL of the solution was taken and analyzed by UV-vis spectroscopy, returning it to the beaker after the measurement. The amount of released CIPh was determined by comparing the absorbance signal at 275 nm (maximum absorbance wavelength of CIPh) with a standard calibration curve. The cumulative drug release (CR) at each time interval was calculated using Eq. 2:

$$CR (\%) = \frac{m_t}{m_0} \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where m_t is the cumulative mass of CIPh released at time t and m_0 is the total amount of CIPh loaded.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the hydrogels were obtained with a JEOL JSM-6400 equipment with an operation voltage of 5 kV. Samples were freeze-dried after being swollen in distilled water and gold coated prior to the measurements.

The *in vitro* cell viability and proliferation in CNC containing hydrogels was analyzed by short-term cytotoxicity assays. Measurements were carried out using L929 mouse fibroblasts cells and following ISO 10993 standard. Briefly, sterilized samples were incubated separately in complete cell culture medium (Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium) plus 10% fetal calf serum supplemented with antibiotics (100 U mL⁻¹ penicillin and 100 g mL⁻¹ of streptomycin) at 37 °C for 24 h to obtain the extracted culture medium. In addition, L929 mouse fibroblast were seeded and allowed to grow in 96-well microplates at a density of 4 x 10³ cells/well in the presence of standard culture medium for 2 h before the experiments. In the cytotoxicity test, cultures were treated for 24 and 48 h with the extracted media. As controls, standard culture media (negative control) and 10% DMSO (positive control) were used.

The metabolic activity of viable cells was determined using the colorimetric MTT assay, in which 3-(4,5-dimethyltriazol-2-yl)-2,5 diphenyltetra-sodium bromide is reduced to formazan in the mitochondria of living cells. The cell number per well was proportional to the amount of formazan crystals and was determined by measuring the absorbance at 540 nm using a microplate reader.

Viability (%) was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Viability (\%)} = \frac{[A]_{\text{test}}}{[A]_{\text{control}}} \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

where $[A]_{\text{test}}$ is the absorbance of the sample cells and $[A]_{\text{control}}$ is the absorbance of the negative control cells. All assays were conducted in triplicate and mean values and their standard deviations were calculated.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the synthesized starch-based DA hydrogels

Hydrogels were prepared by DA cross-linking reaction of furan-modified starch with a commercial tetrafunctional maleimide. The obtained hydrogels resulted in solid-like robust materials that maintained the shape in their hydrated state (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Image of the synthesized hydrogels after the DA reaction.

The chemical structure of the hydrogels was analyzed by infrared spectroscopy. Figure 2a shows the obtained FTIR spectrum in comparison with that of the modified starch (S-FI). For a better understanding of the results, the magnification of the spectra in the range of $2000 - 800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is only shown.

As it could be observed, the spectrum of the obtained hydrogel showed a new peak related to the carbonyl maleimide groups ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) located at 1706 cm^{-1} [27]. In addition, the following new peaks associated to the formation of the DA adduct could also be observed. On one hand, a peak that is usually ascribed to the stretching vibration of the double bond ($\text{C}=\text{C}$) in the DA adduct [14,20,21,28] appeared at 1466 cm^{-1} . Besides, the peak centered at 1105 cm^{-1} is associated with the stretching vibration of the ether linkage ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$) in the DA cycle [27]. However, due to the numerous signals that appeared in the same region the verification of the DA reaction was difficult only based on the FTIR spectra.

Thus, in order to verify the DA reaction, UV-vis spectroscopy was employed. The measurements were performed at $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using a temperature-controller device and collecting spectra every 30 min during a total reaction time of 24 hours. The obtained results are shown in Figure 2b.

During the DA cycloaddition the maleimide groups of the cross-linker reacted with the pendant furan group of the starch to form the DA adduct. Therefore, as the reaction proceeded, the quantity of accessible maleimide groups was expected to decrease. As it has been reported, maleimide compounds showed an absorbance signal with a maximum value near 290 nm [29,30] due to the conjugation effect of the double bond $\pi\pi^*$ (C=C) and the two carbonyl groups $n\pi^*$ (C=O) chromophore excitations of the maleimide ring [27,31]. Thus, the DA reaction could be corroborated by monitoring the evolution of the mentioned absorbance signal since it would decrease due to the disappearance of the conjugation as a consequence of the adduct formation [29,32,33].

As observed in Figure 2b, the absorbance peak associated with the maleimide ring decreased as the reaction proceeded and after 24 hours the signal was not detectable, indicating the consumption of the maleimide to form the DA adduct. Consequently, it was demonstrated that the maleimide groups reacted completely after the reaction time, and thus, the DA reaction proceed satisfactorily.

Figure 2 – a) FTIR spectra magnification of S-FI and the cross-linked starch hydrogel in the range of 2000 - 800 cm^{-1} at room temperature and b) UV-vis spectra of the evolution of the DA reaction at 65 °C.

3.2. Characterization of the nanocomposites

The nanocomposite hydrogels were prepared by adding CNC as nanoreinforcement at 2.5 and 5 wt.%. Several attempts were made to increase the nanocrystal content above the 5 wt.%, but unfortunately, it was not feasible since the mixture resulted extremely viscous and non-homogeneous. However, due to the good nanofiller/matrix affinity and the nanoscale dimensions of the nanofiller, it was expected that the addition of CNCs would contribute to the improvement of the mechanical properties and, at the same time, modulate the swelling and/or the capacity for sustained delivery of drugs of the developed novel hydrogels. Thus, the influence of the CNC content in the rheological behavior, swelling capacity and microstructure was analyzed. Besides, the drug delivery profiles of the antibiotic and the cytotoxicity were also studied.

The viscoelastic behavior of unfilled and nanoreinforced hydrogels was studied by rheological measurements. Firstly, preliminary strain sweep tests were performed in order to determine the linear viscoelastic region of each sample where both the storage (G') and loss modulus (G'') were independent of the applied strain. Thus, a constant strain of 1% was selected to perform the frequency sweep tests. G' and G'' vs frequency curves are presented in Figure 3.

As it could be observed, both the matrix and the nanocomposite hydrogels showed the typical viscoelastic pattern of cross-linked solid gels, being their G' almost constant in the studied frequency range and always higher than G'' [34]. Besides, the significantly high value of G' ($> 10^3$ Pa) indicated a cross-linked permanent robust network formation leading to a rigid and strong behavior [35] along with physical interactions and chain entanglements.

As expected, the addition of CNC led to the increase of the G' value, measuring 1381 Pa for unfilled hydrogel and 2011 Pa for the HSFI4-5CNC hydrogel. Therefore, it could be corroborated the effective contribution of CNC to the elasticity of the hydrogel [35] since the addition of CNC into the matrix increased the efficiency of the network. Indeed, during the DA reaction the CNCs were trapped into

the hydrogel network leading to the formation of intermolecular H-bonds between the primary and secondary OH groups of the CNCs and those of the starch macromolecule. It is worth noting that preliminary investigations developed in our group with gelatin based DA hydrogels reinforced with CNCs [36] found that the addition of not functionalized CNCs did not improve the G' value of the hydrogel. Recently, Kumar et al. [37] developed hybrid polyacrylamide/carboxymethyl cellulose hydrogels and also observed that the addition of 2.5 wt.% of CNCs to the hydrogel matrix was not enough to increase the G' value. On the contrary, in the case of our starch hydrogel the improvement was achieved using bare nanocrystals and, furthermore, the elastic solid-like behavior was measured even at the lowest frequency values, what is indicative of permanent covalent DA cross-links.

Figure 3 – Frequency sweep measurements of ■ HSF14, ▲ HSF14-2.5CNC and ● HSF14-5CNC: G' (filled symbols) and G'' (empty symbols). Tests conditions: 37 °C and 10 Hz.

In order to assess the use of the synthesized hydrogels as sustained drug delivery systems, the swelling capacity of the CNC containing starch-based hydrogels was gravimetrically measured by swelling freeze-dried samples ($n = 3$) in simulated intestinal fluid (PBS, at 37 °C and pH = 7.4). The swelling capacity of the hydrogels would determine the release mechanisms of entrapped drug from

the swollen network. Solute transport within hydrogels occurs primarily through the water-filled regions and, thus, any factor that modifies the size of these spaces will have an effect on the movement of the solute [38]. The swelling ratio (SR) was determined using the Equation 1. The obtaining SR vs time curves are presented in Figure 4.

It was noticed that the swelling patterns of all samples occurred in different two steps. During the first period, the SR increased rapidly, while during the second step the SR increased slowly until the hydrogel acquired the maximum amount of fluid that is able to retain and, thus, achieved the equilibrium. As it could be observed in the Figure 4, the swelling equilibrium was achieved earlier for the unfilled hydrogel that also showed the highest SR value in the first period.

On the other hand, the SR value decreased due to the incorporation of CNCs. As it is well known [10], the SR of hydrogels depends on numerous factors that involves the employed external stimuli (ionic strength, pH or temperature) and the nature of the polymer, i.e. the hydrophilic character of the polymer, the concentration, the cross-linking density of the network and the porosity of the hydrogel. The results, in agreement with those reported by other authors [39,40], revealed that the SR value of polysaccharide-based hydrogels decreased by the addition of CNC as nanofiller. It is assumed that the H-bonding interactions formed between the CNCs and the polysaccharide, starch in our case, reduced the mobility of the network [39] and prevented the permeation of the solution inside the hydrogel. Thus, increasing the CNC content the mobility of the cross-linked network was hindered, leading to lower amounts of permeated PBS and lower SR values.

Figure 4 – SR versus time curves of HSF14, HSF14-2.5CNC and HSF14-5CNC in PBS at 37 °C.

The synthesized hydrogels were evaluated in terms of their ability as sustained release drug delivery systems using ClPh as model drug. The loaded amount of this general antibiotic was found to be similar in all cases, i.e. drug loaded values of 1.58, 1.57 and 1.61 mg ClPh g⁻¹ hydrogel were obtained for unfilled hydrogels and hydrogels reinforced with 2.5 and 5 wt.% of CNC, respectively, and were close to those obtained previously with gelatin based DA crosslinked hydrogels [38]. Drug release studies were then performed at 37 °C during 4 h in PBS that simulates intestinal pH conditions. During the test an aliquot of the released media was analyzed by UV-vis spectroscopy each 30 min returning the aliquot to the beaker once analyzed. The obtained CR profiles are shown in Figure 5.

As it could be observed, in all cases controlled and sustained delivery of the antibiotic was achieved but significant differences were detected between the three hydrogels. In the case of nanocomposites, the drug release presented a two-step pattern. Firstly, the drug delivery occurred rapidly whereas during the second step, a sustained delivery of the antibiotic was observed. Nonetheless, in the case of the unfilled hydrogel the CR profile was more sustained and the initial

burst effect lower. In addition, it should be noted that higher CR values and increasing initial release slope were observed as the CNC content increased.

Figure 5 – Drug release profiles in PBS at 37 °C of HSF14, HSF14-2.5CNC and HSF14-5CNC.

Drug release kinetics will be strongly influenced by the morphology, the inner pore structure and the pore size and distribution [39]. In fact, as explained, achieving an interconnected porous structure is a key issue and decisive to consider in the formation of hydrogels for several biomedical applications [6,30]. Hence, the morphology of the unfilled matrix and the resulting nanocomposite hydrogels was analyzed by SEM over freeze-dried samples after being swollen in distilled water. As stated elsewhere [10,14], when swollen samples are freeze-dried the interconnected domains occupied by water changed to a porous structure due to the ice crystals formation. Figure 6 shows the microstructure of each sample analyzed by SEM.

As it could be observed, all samples presented an interconnected porous microstructure. However, the pore size was notably influenced by the content of the CNC, resulting in higher pore size while increasing the CNC content. Indeed, adding 5 wt.% of CNC the pore size increased from values next to 10 μm to values near 90 μm . Similar behavior was observed by other authors with hydrogels based

on cyclodextrin/triblock copolymer and reinforced with cellulose and chitin NCs [35], concluding that both the pore size and the thickness of the wall increased with the NC content. It seemed that the H-bonds formed during the hydrogel formation in the presence of CNCs, hindered the compaction of the polymeric network and thus, the obtained pore size for nanocomposite hydrogels was notably larger.

The observed effect of the CNCs incorporation in the internal morphology and the pore size of the hydrogels could be related to the previously discussed swelling and drug release behavior. Indeed, the pore distribution and size is generally assumed to be crucial for the swelling capacity as well as to affect the release of the drug [39]. As concluded by SEM images the pore size increased notably due to the addition of CNC what could be the reason for the initial burst release that was observed for nanocomposite hydrogels by comparing with the more sustained profile of the unfilled one. This phenomenon is usually ascribed to the release of the drug fixed to the surface or within the upper layers of the hydrogel instead the release of the drug absorbed inside the polymeric network [41]. However, even if the burst effect it is often regarded as a negative consequence of creating long-term controlled release devices, in certain situations, rapid release or high initial rates of delivery may be desirable, i.e. wound treatments, targeted delivery or pulsatile release [42].

Figure 6 – SEM images of the porous microstructure of HSF14, HSF14-2.5CNC and HSF14-5CNC hydrogels.

Since these hydrogels were developed as possible candidates to be used in the biomedical field, *in vitro* cell viability and proliferation was studied by short-term cytotoxicity assays evaluating changes in cellular growth, incubating L 929 mouse fibroblast cells for 24 h and 48 h in the hydrogels. The obtained results are shown in Figure 7a and b.

Preliminary viability results showed that the hydrogels presented non-toxic behavior and allowed the cell growth. The proliferation curve of hydrogels (Figure 7a) showed the same increasing pattern of the negative control, whereas the positive control presented decreasing slope for the proliferation curve. As mentioned, the cell viability was measured up to 48 hours in cells cultured in extracted medium from hydrogels, showing cell viability values higher than the acceptance limit of 70% (compared with the negative control) as established by ISO 10993-12 standard. Indeed, values of 89.0, 82.6 and 98.0%, were obtained for the unfilled hydrogel and samples reinforced with 2.5 and 5 wt.% of CNC, respectively. These results are in concordance with those published by other authors [35,39,43], where different hydrogel matrixes reinforced with CNC presented good cytocompatibility. Similarly, it could be concluded that the prepared starch-based hydrogels could be initially considered as biocompatible, and thus, would be suitable for biomedical applications.

Figure 7 – (a) Absorbance at 540 nm versus incubation time of a positive control, negative control and HSF14, HSF14-2.5CNC and HSF14-5CNC hydrogels and b) Viability of L-929 murine fibroblast cells in extracted media at 48 h of positive control and HSF14, HSF14-2.5CNC and HSF14-5CNC hydrogels.

4. Conclusions

Starch cross-linked hydrogel nanocomposites were satisfactorily prepared by DA click reaction in aqueous media between synthesized furanic starch derivative (S-FI) and tetrafunctional maleimide cross-linker (TTMI). Firstly, the success of the DA reaction was corroborated by FTIR and UV-vis spectroscopy. In addition, hydrogel nanocomposites were prepared adding different CNC contents (2.5 and 5 wt.%). The results demonstrated that the addition of CNC led to slightly higher storage modulus and lower SR values, influencing notably both the morphology of the hydrogels, with larger pores and thicker walls, and, particularly, the drug delivery performance of the materials. Finally, it

was found that the prepared hydrogels showed non-toxic behavior and cell viability, concluding that they could be proposed as candidates for being applied as sustained drug delivery systems.

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